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ABSTRACT

We describe the design, fabrication and installation of first generation grating-based dielectric laser acceleration structures for first experimental investigations at the Accelerator Research Experiment at SINBAD (ARES) test facility at DESY. We also provide a brief update on the status of the ARES linac, laser, and experimental area.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

This report provides an update on the first generation grating structures, which will be used to demonstrate dielectric laser acceleration with short bunches at ~100 MeV. The report discusses primarily the design of the grating structures, their construction, and their recent installation for first experiments.

We also provide an update on experimental preparations, discussing the current status of the ARES (Accelerator Research Experiment at SINBAD) linac, the 2 micron laser system, laser transportation, and the plan for the near future to conduct first experiments in summer 2020.

1. Introduction

Radiofrequency (RF) accelerators have flourished in the last decades to support today's modern colliders and XFELs. Despite their widespread developmental progress, it is clear that RF accelerators are inherently limited in several aspects, e.g. in synchronization at the ~10 fs level, in acceleration gradients below ~100 MV/m, in limited repetition rates for normal conducting RF (~100 Hz), and finally, they generally require relatively large footprints.

The development of laser-based accelerators is an attractive concept where the small quasi-optical wavelengths have much larger energy densities, supporting larger (GV/m) accelerating gradients in compact dielectric structures. Moreover, lasers also support large (MHz) repetition rates, can be well synchronized, and have relatively compact footprints.

The last several years have shown first demonstrations of particle acceleration using dielectric grating structures [1-3]. These structures are produced via lithography and typically support an accelerating channel on the order of the driving wavelength, with accelerating channel lengths of ~1 mm. Each grating tooth provides sufficient delay to the expected decelerating phases such that a properly phased electron bunch will always accelerate.

This report is organized as follows: we discuss the design, construction, and installation of our grating dielectric structures. We then discuss the current situation at DESY and forecast to first experiments.

2. Grating-type Dielectric Laser Accelerators (DLAs)

1.1 DESIGN OF DIELECTRIC GRATING STRUCTURES

DESY's participation in the accelerator on a chip (ACHIP¹) program has motivated the usage of grating structures in the first round of experiments at the ARES (Accelerator Research Experiment at SINBAD) test stand of the SINBAD (Short Innovative Bunches and Accelerators at DESY) accelerator research facility.

Two different designs were developed based on the fabrication techniques from our partners at Erlangen, Germany and Stanford, USA. The designs for both structures are similar but differ primarily due to different substrates materials and fabrication techniques. Based on the success of previous experiments at SLAC [2] and consecutive experiments at UCLA [3], we designed a similar type of grating structure which could be fabricated by Solgaard's group at Stanford. The structure is a double grating-design with fused silica substrates. A second structure was designed and fabricated by the Hommelhoff group at FAU, Erlangen, consisting of a double pillar structure in silicon. The designs were optimized using the CST electromagnetic simulations code with respect to particle transmission and acceleration gradient. Figure 1 illustrates the patterns of the non-vanishing field components. Acceleration gradients of ~ 1 GV/m are expected from the designs.

Figure 1: CST simulation results illustrating the various field components of the accelerating mode.

Previous DLA experimental research has demonstrated the presence of energy modulations where equal amounts of electrons were accelerated and decelerated. At SINBAD we will explore acceleration with longer wavelengths and with relatively short ($\sigma_z < \lambda/2$) electron bunch lengths allowing for acceleration with significantly lower energy spreads. A suitable working point of the ARES linac was simulated with the ASTRA [4] and Ocelot [5] codes. The results (see Table 1) guide the DLA design, where we optimize the gap size for transmission and total energy gain (Fig. 2).

¹ <https://achip.stanford.edu/>

Parameter	Value
Bunch length (FWHM)	~1.7 fs
σ_x	~1.5 μm
σ_y	~10 μm
Mean energy	95 MeV
Charge	0.5 pC

Table 1: Simulated ARES beam parameters at EAI (Experimental Area 1).

Fused silica design

Param	Value
A	1790 nm
B	1025 nm
D	1025 nm
L	1 mm
λ (laser)	2050 nm

Figure 2: Design of the grating structure fabricated by Stanford.

Figure 3 (blue trace) shows the mean acceleration gradient over the gap region normalized to the field amplitude of the incident laser for a double grating with single sided illumination. The orange trace shows the standard deviation of the samples over the gap region and is a measure for the uniformity of the field over the gap. Two sample types were produced with a 1000 nm and 2300 nm gap.

Figure 3: Scan of the gap between two gratings with single-sided illumination showing the acceleration gradient normalized to the incident field amplitude and the standard deviation of the samples across the gap as a measure of uniformity is shown.

1.2 FABRICATION OF DIELECTRIC GRATING STRUCTURES

After optimizing the grating designs, we subsequently received the structures in the Q4, 2019 from both groups. We note here, that due to the substantially larger damage thresholds of fused silica compared to silicon, the Stanford structures are preferred. The Stanford structures were fabricated with UV lithography while the structures from Erlangen were produced via electron beam lithography. Below in Fig. 4, SEM photographs of the structures acquired from Stanford are shown.

Figure 4: An SEM photograph of the grating structure produced by Stanford.

1.3 MOUNTING OF GRATING STRUCTURES FOR ALIGNMENT TESTS AND EXPERIMENTS

In February 2020, the Stanford grating structures were mounted into the vacuum compatible structures. The structures are extremely fragile; two structures were unfortunately destroyed during mounting. Two structures were however, successfully mounted into the structure mounts developed for our experimental campaign, shown Fig. 5. The mounted structures have a 2 μm channel gap/aperture, one additional structure from Stanford remains with a 1 μm channel gap. In addition, we also have the Erlangen pillar structures for other possible experiments. Acquiring more structures from Stanford is also under discussion. The mounted structures are now ready and approved by the machine vacuum group, awaiting installation as of February 2020.

Figure 5: The mounted grating structures are shown on the mounting blocks on a temporary aluminium holder.

3. Experimental preparation

We briefly give a status update on the experimental preparations at DESY for first experiments including an update on the LINAC commissioning, laser development, laser transport, and the experimental area.

1.4 STATUS OF THE ARES LINAC

The first photoelectron beam was produced and measured on October 31, 2019 (Fig. 6). Since then, the machine has been under development to condition the RF structures, align solenoid magnets, cathode exchange, beam alignment etc. We have unfortunately experienced a large dark current problem which has required the installation of a new gun; the gun installation is planned in first week of March 2020. We note, the new gun also incorporates a modified design that will allow the addition of a bucking solenoid to reduce the beam emittance, especially at higher charges.

Figure 6: Photograph of the first electron beam measured at ARES.

1.5 LASER STATUS

The 2 μm laser system is operational, delivering ~ 1.6 mJ at 5 kHz and can possibly be increased up to ~ 2.1 mJ. Frequency-resolved optical gating (FROG) measurements indicate a pulse length of 1.5 ps. A new oscillator is being developed to synchronize the laser system with the ARES timing system, expected to be completed in Q2, 2020. Furthermore, a pulse picker has also been installed to lower the repetition rate to e.g. reduce average power on the structures.

1.6 TRANSPORT

The laser beamline is being installed and is expected to be completed in early March (Figure 7). Alignment of the beamline has begun for the various components and first laser alignment work will begin in end of February. We await the delivery of final elements of the beamline for final assembly.

Figure 7: CAD rendering of the experimental area with the laser beamline.

1.7 EXPERIMENTAL AREA

The experimental chamber has been installed and aligned, see Fig. 8. After vacuum work is completed in the final week of February, the installation of the optical table is planned. Thereafter, the mounting of the periscope will occur, with first 2 μm laser beam transport anticipated in the coming weeks. Currently we have begun alignment work on the 2 μm telescope system which will be used to measure beam sizes at the experimental area. Some problems have been found and appropriate measures are underway.

Figure 8: Installation of the EA1 chamber is shown (left). View from the top flange of the chamber is shown (right). The hexapod is visible along with a mounting plate. A lens is visible which is used in the microscope configuration to measure small beam sizes.

4. Investigation into alternative structures

In our previous milestone report, we discussed the use of a photonic crystal fibre (PCF). While this work is very interesting and promising as a fully scalable laser accelerator, it is unfortunately not compatible with our laser system. We would require the purchase of a new laser system, or the development of a narrowband optical parametric amplifier for compatibility, see reference [6].

Since this work, we have investigated beam dynamics in an alternative acceleration structure in collaboration with P. Russell at the Max Planck Institute for Light (MPL). However, these results have not yet been published and therefore cannot be included in this report. We have instead provided an internal, non-public document on this work to the ARIES collaborators. We aim for the manuscript to be submitted to PRAB in Q4 2020.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
DLA	Dielectric laser acceleration/accelerator
PCF	Photonic crystal fibre
Xfel	x-ray free electron laser
Ea1	Experimental area 1